

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CULTURAL REST

Nasirdinov Murot Toyshiboevich

Teacher of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7638288>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the labor activity of people, the role of free time in human life, effective use of free time, the distribution of weekly working hours, categories of cultural leisure forms and their analysis.

Keywords: annual rest time, work, physical labor, working time, free time, necessary time, weekly rest time, person, society, culture.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, in May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

As much as it is necessary for a person to work and engage in some activity, it is also a natural need for him to write off his physical and mental fatigue, to rest, and to have cultural recreation. Just as there is no equipment or mechanism that works forever, it is impossible to have a person who works non-stop without rest. Maintaining a balance between work, physical and mental stress levels, and rest and relaxation is a guarantee of a person’s healthy functioning and effective work.

English philosopher Thomas More dealt with the problem of the role and importance of free time in society and human life as early as the 16th century, and revealed the essence of this social phenomenon in his work “Utopia”. Later, the Italian philosopher Tommaso Campanella supported T. More’s ideas in his books “The City of the Sun” and English scientist Francis Bacon “New Atlantis”. In the new era, many philosophers and sociologists in the world were engaged in the phenomenon of free time.

Usually, a person rests in his free time, engages in various cultural and recreational activities, and is free from fatigue and prepares himself for a new work process. So, how much free time is created for each person to relax after work, to develop physically and spiritually, to engage in useful activities according to his interests, depends on the humanity of the society. indicates the priority of the rules of justice. Thanks to independence, the age-old dreams of our people have come true, and the need to spend their free time after work and study in a meaningful and productive way has increased. Therefore, in our country, it is necessary to improve the health of the population on a large scale, to provide social protection, to realize the creative and

intellectual potential of young people, and to fully meet the requirements of the 21st century, which is today's fast-paced and science-technologically developed to an unprecedented level. special importance is attached to the issues of implementation of clearly directed measures to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for raising all-around well-rounded individuals.

Usually, a person's time is divided into two - working time and non-working time. Working time is the amount of time spent on production, creation of society's material wealth, satisfaction of personal material needs. The purpose of such work is not only to satisfy personal needs, but also to develop the wealth of the society and to strengthen the material and technical base of the country. Working time accounts for 17% of the annual time budget on average. Non-working time means the time necessary for human life and free time for recreation, in addition to the defined socially useful working time.

Necessary time - necessary moments to meet the needs of human life and livelihood. It can be roughly divided into the following parts: a) lunch break related to the work process, time spent on going to and from work; b) time spent on family needs, raising children, preparing food, going to the market, buying necessary items from stores, arranging household appliances, clothes; c) time spent on physiological needs, food, hygiene and sleep.

Free time is the time spent for relaxation, release of fatigue, spiritual and physical development. How to use it is up to everyone. In free time, you can engage in many activities, such as improving knowledge and skills, engaging in social and political activities, sports and amateur creativity, cultural recreation, and hiking.

It can be seen that it is very difficult to set a limit between necessary and free time outside of work, to determine its exact amount. However, if the weekly time budget consists of 168 hours, approximately 40 hours will be working time, 50 hours will be spent sleeping, 34 hours will be free time, and more than 44 hours will be necessary work. while going to meet household needs and so on.

If we divide the daily (24 hours) total time budget of people into 4 parts, one part of it is working time (7-8 hours), the second part is free time (4-5 hours), and the third part is sleep (7-8 hours), while the rest is made up of other necessary activities - commuting to work, walking, etc. (4-5 hours).

According to sociologists, the free time of city dwellers was 34-36 hours per week, and the free time of workers in rural areas was 28-32 hours. The free time of the city dwellers is almost equal to their main working time and is about 1700 hours a year. It turns out that free time is about 17-19% of the annual time budget. According to the amount of free time, rest time is divided into the following, i.e., daily rest, weekly rest days, public holidays and annual rest. Daily recreation includes leisure activities during the day, from the time of work to bedtime. Common daily leisure activities include walking in the fresh air, listening to and watching radio and television programs, reading books, and doing physical education.

Weekly off - includes activities on Saturday and Sunday. Recommended activities on these days off include going to parks on the outskirts of the city, visiting relatives and friends, and doing household chores. Activities of culture, art institutions and sports clubs are of particular importance in the meaningful and enjoyable passage of daily and weekly holidays.

Usually moments of joy, joy and rest full of joy happen on holidays. People prepare for the holidays in advance, wear their best clothes, and prepare delicious food. On these days, radio, television, art and club institutions present their best programs. Demonstrations and marches, various shows are organized in parks, avenues, and streets. So, holidays can be said to be the most enjoyable and productive moments of rest.

Annual leave includes legally paid annual leave-working leave. In order to effectively relax and strengthen health during vacations, workers are given passes to holiday homes, sanatoriums, and tourist centers. During the working holiday, it is recommended not to engage in the main work, to change the weather and environmental conditions, to rest in beautiful and healing places of nature. It goes without saying that more free time during the holidays creates opportunities for people to volunteer.

Cultural-recreational activity usually means that people spend their free time with active cultural recreation. But it is important not to forget that human life and practical activities are very diverse and colorful. Accordingly, the forms and means of recreation are different.

As a result of scientific and technical progress, the organization of cultural recreation of the population has become one of the most important issues at the present time, when manual labor is increasingly mechanized and free time is increasing. Therefore, at the core of free time there are unlimited opportunities for the development of the individual and the whole society, for people to become spiritually enriched, to be healthy, to add life to their lives, to make their lives more meaningful and colorful.

As we dwell on the issues of rational use of free time, first of all, it should be noted that free time is an invaluable resource that is among the necessary factors for the development of the individual and society. Because free time is considered a social asset and serves for the development of personality and spirituality. After all, free time is an important factor in increasing labor productivity. Our people say, "A good rest is a sympathy for hard work". If a person works well and productively, he feels the need for effective and meaningful rest. In turn, it is worth noting that a person who does not have a good rest cannot work as hard as he wants. Therefore, effective use of free time means restoring people's energy spent in the process of work, improving their health, and refreshing their spirits.

According to the research conducted at the bases of industrial enterprises in Tashkent, Fergana, Margilan, Kokan, after specially organized rest days in recreation zones, labor productivity of some workers was 26-31% higher than usual, i.e. 26% in men, 31% in women. Sociological studies conducted by the All-Union Scientific Research Institute of Art Studies show that the labor productivity of people who often attend events of cultural institutions such as theaters, museums, clubs, or those who play sports is higher than others, i.e. It is 10-15% higher than those who spend their time idle.

As a result of not appreciating free time, not using it rationally, and not creating the necessary conditions for the relaxation process of workers in time, which interconnects human life, work, and livelihood and plays an important role in their development. serious social problems arose during the recession years.

The problems that arose as a result of not being able to adequately evaluate free time and use it wisely were reflected in all areas. Many negative events in places, failure to fulfill the plan in production, low quality of products, violation of labor discipline, occurrence of drunkenness on

weekends after work, increase of sick people, creation of unhealthy environment in many communities, war in families - The increase in the divorce of husband and wife due to quarrels, the violation of children's upbringing, and their entry into the streets of hooliganism are also, in a certain sense, the consequence of not paying enough attention to the free time of the population.

The inner spiritual world and psychology of a person is structured in such a way that he strives to enjoy the beauties of life. Free time is a convenient opportunity for this. But since special conditions are not created for people to enjoy and enjoy their free time, some people try to achieve this by artificial means, that is, by consuming alcoholic beverages. Consumption of alcoholic beverages by people in their free time, firstly, if it harms their health, secondly, it creates the ground for an unhealthy situation in the family and community, and finally, it paves the way for criminal activities. possible

Currently, the fight against alcoholism by paying attention to spiritual, cultural and educational activities is bearing its fruits. However, this is not enough. That's why we need to explain to the general public the forms of cultural recreation that gradually eliminate alcoholism from life. In particular, it is necessary to create such a cultural environment and environment in places so that people can enjoy life in their free time, not artificially, but naturally, from the beauty of nature, from folk art, from rituals, as well as from the products of their creative work. let them enjoy. Indeed, the effective use of free time is one of the most important tasks for working people, and especially young people, and now more than ever it is being paid attention to. To search for new promising ways of rational use of free time, to make fuller use of existing reserves and opportunities, to develop local club institutions, sports facilities and other recreation centers, their requires strengthening the material and technical base to improve the level of work.

Thus, free time is, firstly, cultural rest, recreation, recovery of spent forces, secondly - acquisition of cultural and educational wealth, thirdly, creative and physical activities, physical culture, sports and artistic hobby. engage in, fourthly, volunteer community work, types of socially useful work — useful work for the development of society, necessary for impartial service.

A person who uses every minute of free time in a planned, wise and effective way can achieve many things in life. Renowned sociologist S.N. Analyzing the results of many studies in her book “Conversations about Culture”, Ikonnikova points out six categories of people who use their free time differently:

People of the first category value their free time very much and try to use it in every possible way. Every hour and minute counts, and interesting and important things and events do not escape their attention. Such people strive to be aware of interesting books, plays, movies, concerts, exhibitions, and even regret it if they don't have enough time to get acquainted with any cultural event in their cultural life.

People of the second category are focused on one activity, and they spend their free time on things related to their interest. They are actively engaged in sports, artistic hobby or other individual type of creativity.

People belonging to the third category dedicate their free time to their profession, engage in activities that are difficult to perform during the main working hours, try to improve their skills,

create new things, and strive for inventiveness. Such people include more scientists, artists, writers. They can also be found among agricultural workers, labor-rationalizers and technicians.

People of the fourth category include those who tend to spend their free time mainly at home. They go to theaters, movies, clubs, parks and relax. And they can watch TV from morning till night.

Fifth graders try to spend their free time with acquaintances, friends, and colleagues. When such people are alone, they are not interested in anything, when they fall into random companies, they join in any activity, they get bored of being alone, they cannot do independent work.

People of the sixth category are not interested in anything, do not value time at all, and do not regret that life is passing by in vain. It is enough for such spiritually poor people to have food, clothes, and other things for them, as long as no one disturbs them.

The human body is structured in such a way that it regularly repeats various types of activities. Nevertheless, most people are mostly engaged in the same activity. Including:

- Intellectual activity: it is more often manifested in the work of scientists, creative workers, scientific and technical workers.
- Physical activity: mainly manifested in the work of workers, farmers, athletes, servants.
- Emotional-spiritual activity: manifested in teachers, doctors, educators, actors, artists and other professions.[4]

The more these three types of activities are exchanged in the daily life of each person, the more normal he lives and the better his abilities develop. If a person is busy with physical work, he may not improve mentally, or if he does only mental work, he may weaken physically. Therefore, it is better for those who engage in mental activity during work to use types of recreation related to physical activity in their free time. On the other hand, people who are busy with physical work will get better results if they engage in mental activities. So, it means rest, change of activity. Leo Tolstoy used the change of activity very effectively in his life. Along with writing his world-famous novels, he taught at school, jogged, and rode a bicycle. That's why Leo Tolstoy achieved great success in his artistic creation and lived a long time. Thus, it is necessary to choose the activity that should be engaged in free time, first of all, based on the nature of the main work, labor, and profession. A person should strive to develop abilities that are not realized in the course of his work in his free time.

It is known that rest time is a part of free time, and first of all, it serves to restore the energy spent in the production of a person, to release his fatigue. Cultural leisure is one of the important factors in a person's spiritual-aesthetic maturity, physical health, and having a broad worldview, using free time wisely. This form of recreation is being given a lot of attention in the future. This, in turn, makes it possible to improve the culture of recreation.

According to the calculations of modern sociologists, there are 500 types of activities that can be done in addition to the main job. They include daily chores, from shaving to bathing, from medical treatment to hospitality, from yard work to pet care, from home maintenance to fishing. 150 of the free time activities can be used as recreational activities (their main groups include continuous education and professional development, community work, hobby, sports, etc. (including interacting with students, enjoying artwork, etc.). Forms of productive use of free

time and cultural recreation can be conditionally divided into 4 categories. In each category, forms of recreation become more complex and more effective.[5]

The first category includes the simplest forms of recreation - low-motion leisure and fatigue-dissolving activities. The second category of forms of leisure is the acquisition of cultural and spiritual resources, i.e. reading books, newspapers, magazines, listening to and watching radio and television programs, movies, plays and art shows in theaters, cinemas and clubs. such as watching public scenes. The third category of recreation includes creative and physical activities, that is, participation in artistic hobby, physical culture and sports clubs.

The fourth category of recreation includes socially useful activities - public works, work outside of work, educational communities, and the implementation of tasks necessary for the residents of residential areas. This is a voluntary and at the same time useful work for the development of society - impartial service.

As there are various methods and forms of free time use in practice, its three main types are distinguished in scientific literature. These are:

1. Creative type. As the name suggests, the most important activities that attract an individual are those that help to realize his creative intentions. One thing is that a person works diligently to realize his creative intentions. Even in what field this creative activity is (literature, art, technology, etc.), whether the final result expected from it is a material or spiritual product - regardless of this, an individual is free to create. he spends his time, because this work is his heart's work, a means of expressing his personality and spiritual world.

2. Type of cultural consumption. A distinctive feature of this type is that the individual spends his free time in communication with spiritual resources and strives to increase his spiritual culture. Acquiring cultural and spiritual wealth, that is, going to libraries and museums, listening to and watching radio and television programs, watching movies and plays shown in theaters, cinemas and clubs. The most important among them is reading books. Art books, scientific and journalistic literature play a very important role in acquiring cultural resources. A book is an important tool that embodies all the knowledge experiences of mankind, an invaluable resource that provides information about the spiritual wealth of the previous generation, the past and present achievements of people. The book serves in the formation of a person, the expansion of knowledge and worldview, mastering the secrets of the profession, and becoming a real expert. At the same time, the book serves to beautify people's lives, ease their work, and make their rest more meaningful. "Each period has its own books. There are books to be read at the time of literacy - unread childhood - stupidity, and there are books to be read at the end of life - unread old age - darkness. While reading a book, every time you get excited, your heart shakes, your cheeks flutter, and every time your eyes are moistened, they are washed and purified.

3. Recreational type ("recreation" in Latin means "to regain health", "recovery"). All types of recreation and entertainment activities belong to this type. Including physical culture and sports, fishing, tourism, going to restaurants, cafes, teahouses, participating in dance parties, sitting with friends, visiting relatives, etc.

It seems that the first and second types of free time seem more meaningful and cultural than the third, but this does not mean that the third type should be abandoned in social and personal life. Moreover, in practice, most people use these types of leisure time alternately.[6]

It should be noted that the processes taking place in the world in recent years have changed the content of free time of many people, including young people. As a result, inclinations aimed at enjoying free time and institutions aimed at serving this area appeared, which can be considered a hedonistic (enjoyment) type. This type of free time includes various morally negative activities, such as drug addiction, alcoholism, prostitution, gambling.

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.
3. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Yuldoshev E. Organization of library funds. Study guide. -Tashkent: 2002. -P.30
5. Islamov E. Yuldoshev E. Organization of the school library. Study guide. -Tashkent: Teacher, 1992.-P.25
6. Yuldoshev E. Guiding children's reading in the library. Study guide. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2002. -P.14